

Colloidal Chemical Analysis. Part I.

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General Introduction.

The present series aims at dealing with the theoretical relationships implied in customary interpretations of results from colloid chemical analysis of inorganic hydrosols. It is intended to deal mainly with the following aspects.—(1) Correlation of the cataphoretic speed with the chemical composition of the colloid and intermiscellary liquid. The need for considering the adsorption of ions in detail for distinguishing between the presence of the ions on the solid and liquid sides of the interface and between electrical and primary adsorption of ions, have been emphasised by us (*Trans., Faraday Soc.*, 1921, **16**, 103; *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, **44**, 305; Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **2**, 296; Chaudhury and Rai-Choudhuri, *ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 493; Rai-Choudhuri and Bhattacharyya, *ibid.*, 1928, **5**, 735; *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, **49**, 362). (2) Measurements on the variation of the charge of colloidal particles in this laboratory show that it is not possible to speak of a *definite* critical coagulation potential independent of the method of preparation of the colloid, of the nature of the electrolyte, and of the degree of dilution (*loc. cit.*). The work of Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **44**, 101) has confirmed this conclusion. It has been shown (Rai-Choudhuri and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*, see also Weiser, *loc. cit.*) that considerations of changes in the dielectric constant (Kruyt and Willigen, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **130**, 170; *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, **44**, 22; Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2693) in the interfacial layer do not suffice to account for the differences in the cataphoretic speeds at the coagulating concentration. It has been contended that a definite critical coagulation potential exists for electrolytes having polyvalent coagulating ions, if not for those having univalent ones. In the following table are given the cataphoretic speeds at the coagulating concentration of arsenious sulphide under different conditions which show that there is no definite critical coagulation potential *even for divalent cations* (Kruyt and Willigen, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, *loc. cit.*; Briggs, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 1326; Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I.

Sol.	Electrolyte and its conc.	Cataphoretic speed $\times 10^5$.	Reference.
Sample I.			
(Diluted 1 : 1)	$\cdot 033$ N-HCl ($C_H = \cdot 031$ N)	45.0**	<i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1926, 2, 303.
„	$\cdot 111$ N-Oxalic ($C_H = \cdot 0333$ N)	36.3**	„
„	2.46 N-Formic ($C_H = \cdot 027$ N)	34.7**	„
„	$\cdot 1$ N-Acetic ($C_H = \cdot 0012$ N)	35.7**	„
Sample II.			
(Diluted 1 : 1)	$\cdot 001$ N-BaCl ₂ + $\cdot 1134$ N-Sodium benzoate.	41	<i>J. Indian. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1927, 4, 508.
„	$\cdot 0015$ N-Calcium benzoate + $\cdot 1134$ N-Sodium benzoate.	36.2	„
„	$\cdot 0015$ N-Calcium benzoate.	9.1*	„
„	$\cdot 001$ N-BaCl ₂ + $\cdot 0375$ N-NaCl.	39.7**	„
„	$\cdot 001$ N-BaCl ₂ .	20.2*	„
„	$\cdot 0015$ N-MgCl ₂ + $\cdot 0375$ N-NaCl.	42.6**	„
„	$\cdot 0015$ N-MgCl ₂ + $\cdot 04$ N-LiCl.	50.4**	„
„	$\cdot 0015$ N-MgCl ₂ .	15.5*	„
Sample III.			
(Diluted 1 : 1)	$\cdot 056$ N-KCl.	68.8	<i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1928, 5, 741.
(Diluted 1 : 5)	$\cdot 067$ N-KCl.	50.6	„
(Diluted 1 : 10)	$\cdot 077$ N-KCl.	47.3	„
Sample IV.			
(Diluted 1 : 1)	$\cdot 055$ N-KCl.	59.9	<i>Kolloid Z.</i> , 1930, 53, 160
„	$\cdot 001$ N-BaCl ₂ .	14.84	„

(3) In several instances (Rai-Choudhury and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*) the coagulating concentration is not affected materially by the initial cataphoretic speed of the colloidal particle or the speed at coagulation and that in a number of cases the cataphoretic speed is

* Coagulation did not occur even at this low cataphoretic speed.

** Near the coagulating region.

different before and after coagulation. Excepting these measurements there are no reliable data in the literature dealing with the cataphoretic speed at coagulating concentrations and the observed time effect and further experimental data would be of interest. (4) The conditions for satisfactory measurements of the cataphoretic speed by the boundary method have been discussed by us (*loc. cit.*). It appears necessary to emphasise them again in relation to measurements which overlook them, because one cannot at all be sure that they are not erroneous. (5) Another point of interest is whether there is a relationship between the cataphoretic speed and the density of free electrical charges on the surface of colloidal particles. (6) In the usual interpretations of the observed reversible E. M. F. of ions in a colloidal solution the following aspect is overlooked and requires to be clearly formulated. It is not known whether the observed electromotive force (for example with a calomel electrode in a colloidal solution of ferric hydroxide containing chloride ions) is to be ascribed simply to the ions present (chlorine in this case) in the intermicellary liquid or to the free ions associated with the charged colloidal particles or to both. (7) Also in investigations on the effects of dilution of a sol on its properties, the theoretical discussions rest upon too simple a picture and the complicated changes that result from dilution are not fully taken into consideration.

Ferric Hydroxide Hydrosol.—The present paper deals with ferric hydroxide hydrosols. As with previous workers, part of the information has to be obtained indirectly. The difficulties in the way of accepting the conclusions of previous investigators as also the need for direct methods will be pointed out. It is hoped to present results of direct measurements in subsequent papers.

Lottermoser and Maffia (*Ber. Ges.*, 1910, **43**, 3613) and Pauli and Matula (*Kolloid Z.*, 1917, **21**, 49) determined the distribution† of chlorine ions between the colloid 'micelle' and the intermicellary liquid. The electrical conductivity of the sol is taken to consist of (a) that contributed by the micelle ions and the *free* oppositely charged electrolytic ions associated with them and (b) that of the electrolytes present in the intermicellary liquid. Maffia claimed that the ultrafiltrate gave the intermicellary liquid in an unchanged condition. "The results obtained by the ultrafilter could be

† Freundlich (*vide infra*) in explaining the equilibrium conditions points out the possibility of the surface changing with the concentration of electrolyte.

confirmed by those in which the intermicellary liquid was allowed to enter into equilibrium with the external liquid by dialysis" (Freundlich, *colloid and Capillary Chemistry, Eng. Ed.*, 1926, p. 372). This proposition has been tacitly assumed by later workers (McBain in connection with his work on soaps; Kruyt and Willigen, *Kolloid Z.*, *loc. cit.*). Pauli and Matula (*loc. cit.*) found from potential measurements that "the hydrogen-ion concentration proved to be not sensibly different from that in neutral solution, nor did it appreciably alter on coagulation by electrolytes. But chlorine-ion concentration suffers great changes on coagulation by electrolytes" (Freundlich, *loc. cit.* p. 374). Rabinovitsch (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 133, 203) has recently investigated the changes in the concentration of oppositely charged ions on the addition of electrolytes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Sol: 10 C.c. of a saturated solution of ferric chloride were added drop by drop to 500 c.c. of boiling conductivity water with constant stirring and boiled for half an hour. The solution when cold was dialysed for a month and a half. It contained a trace of chloride. *The cataphoretic speeds* were measured by the method of moving boundary as improved by Mukherjee (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, A 103, 102). The boundary could be read satisfactorily when a blue glass was placed in front of the light. The upper liquid was prepared as given by S. N. Mukherjee (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 63; see also Rai-Choudhuri and Bhattacharyya *loc. cit.*). *The silver-silver chloride electrodes* were prepared as given by Noyes and Ellis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 2532). The *total chlorine* was determined by electrometric titration using a saturated solution of silver chloride for the reference electrode. A measured volume of the sol was dissolved in nitric acid, the iron precipitated, washed carefully, and the total filtrate collected. To a definite volume acidified with nitric acid, solid potassium nitrate was added so as to make its concentration 5% and titrated with a centinormal silver nitrate solution from a microburette. The titration was continued after the change in the sign of the E.M.F. The coagulating concentrations were determined as given by Chaudhury (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794). The *ultrafiltration* was carried out by means of ultrafilters prepared from a high concentration

of collodion in an open pattern nickel plated ultrafilter. A pump was used for suction. The ultrafilters were carefully washed before use.

The ultrafiltrate was also used as upper liquid in cataphoretic measurements but did not give a satisfactory boundary condition. The potential gradient varied widely during the cataphoresis (*cf. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 593). It is necessary* to draw attention to this observation for the method of moving boundaries gives entirely erroneous results unless the conditions for a satisfactory boundary as defined by Mukherjee are previously ascertained from a direct determination of the potential gradient across the boundary.

The measurement of hydrogen-ion concentrations in this sol present difficulties. Oxygen or glass electrodes may be used but it is doubtful whether they are accurate enough for our purpose. The hydrogen-ion concentrations of the clear liquid obtained by coagulating the sol with a small amount of solid potassium sulphate were determined. It is not known whether they give the correct hydrogen-ion concentration of the intermicellary fluid as stated by Pauli and Matula (*loc. cit.*).

Results.

TABLE II.

Sol A contains .0422 mols of Fe_2O_3 per litre. A/2, A/4 have been obtained by diluting sol A to twice and four times its volume.

Sol.	Time of coagulation in minutes.	Coagulating concentrations (normal).		
		KCl	K_2SO_4	$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$
A	3	.23	.00069	.00 016
A/2	3	.23	.00039	.00013
A/2	6	.21	.00038	.000127
A/4	3	.23	.00028	.00007
A/4	12	.19	.00026	.000067

* *Cf. Freundlich, Kapillar Chemie*, 1930; Pauli, *Electrochemie der Kolloide*, 1929, p. 149; Kruyt and Willigen, *loc. cit.*, where the need for such direct terminations has been overlooked.

TABLE III.

Cataphoretic speeds $\times 10^5$.

Dilution.	Viscosity (taking the value of water as unity at the same temp.).	Speed.		Average speed (reduced to viscosity of water).
		Direct.	Reverse.	
A	1.0396	49.52	50.35	51.43
		49.76	48.66	
		50.23	48.66	
A/2	1.0023	44.04	41.38	41.32
		39.58	41.77	
		41.13	39.57	
A/4	1.0011	49.23	50.28	49.79
A/6	1.0100	53.33	51.12	53.51
		52.6	54.93	
A/11	1.0002	58.21	58.59	58.41

TABLE IV.

Sol.	Specific conduc- tivity in r.o.	Chlorine-ion conc. (normal) (20.5° to 22°).	Total chloride conc. (normal).	C_H (normal). 30°
A	.001039	.003166	.0104	.000369
A/2	.0005601	.00206	.0052*	.000316
A/4	.0003084	.001042	.0026*	.000098
A/6	.0002175	.0006982	.00173*	.0000619
A/11	.0001183	.0004656	.000945*	.0000271

* Calculated from that for Sol A.

TABLE V.
Cataphoretic speeds $\times 10^5$: Sol A/2.

Concentration of potassium chloride (normal).	Direct.	Reverse.	Average (reduced to viscosity of water).
0	44.04 39.58 41.13	41.38 41.77 39.57	41.24
0.001	41.74 41.13	43.26 46.33	43.11
0.01	41.37 43.99	40.51 40.33	41.55
0.05	42.14 38.28	39.39 43.52	40.83
0.067	38.95 43.12	39.59 41.68	40.83
0.1	40.54 41.68	37.93 38.90	39.76
0.125	40.39 40.79	35.91 30.38 (coagulation of sol begins)	39.47
0.125 (after coagulation)	32.58 (about 3 hrs. from starting of experiment). 27.47 (about 4 hrs. from starting of experiment).	33.94 24.54	29.63

TABLE VI.
Cataphoretic speeds $\times 10^5$: Sol A/11.

Concentration of potassium chloride (normal).	Direct.	Reverse.	Average (reduced to viscosity of water).
0	58.21	58.59	58.40
0.0002	51.18 54.21	55.11 58.43	54.73
0.001	51.95 49.65	52.97 52.71	51.82
0.01	39.91 39.41	39.25 39.50	39.51
0.02	37.49 36.17	39.96 40.65	38.56
0.083	33.20*	32.46*	32.83
During coagulation. 0.1	37.03*	26.57 (Coagulates)	—
After coagulation. 0.1	19.85	Particles settle down and boundary gets disturbed.	19.65

* Boundary becomes convex.

TABLE VII. Sol B.

Cataphoretic speeds $\times 10^5$ with different upper liquids including the ultrafiltrate.

Contains 0.0143 mols. of Fe_2O_3 per litre: $p_{\text{H}} = 2.004$.

Upper liquid.	Pot. grad. before cataphoresis.	Pot. grad. after cataphoresis.	Direct movement.	Pot. grad. before cataphoresis.	Pot. grad. after cataphoresis.	Reverse movement.	Average (reduced to viscosity of water).
Equiconducting HCl	1.110	1.138	50.43	1.174	1.176	47.26	49.58
	1.112	1.108	50.96	1.123	1.100	49.96	
	1.132	1.123	50.25	1.141	1.127	48.65	
Ultrafiltrate	1.054	1.009	38.77	1.017	1.075	54.13	46.33
	1.035	0.9895	40.62	1.022	1.080	51.81	
Usual upper liquid	Speed for residual sol after ultrafiltration.						
	1.016	1.046	43.10	1.091	1.034	41.84	42.14
	1.059	1.047	41.14	1.096	1.047	42.51	

TABLE VIII.

Sol B - Analysis.

	Specific conductivity (r.o.).	Chlorine-ion concentration (normal).	Total chloride concentration (normal).
Sol B	0.002563	0.006985	0.008588
Supernatant liq. after coagulation by K_2SO_4	—	0.007408	0.00777
Ultrafiltrate	0.002245* 0.002165	0.005761	0.005932
Residual sol after ultrafiltration	0.002480	0.007408	0.01554

* Specific conductivity of 0.005761 N-hydrochloric acid.

Discussion.

(a) *Changes brought about by dilution.*—In agreement with previous observations the coagulating concentration (Table II) of the divalent and trivalent oppositely charged ions decreases on dilution ; while that for potassium chloride remains constant so long as the time of coagulation remains the same. But if the time is made proportional to the dilution (as suggested by Usher, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 21, 406) the electrolyte also shows a sensitisation, indicating a change in the condition of the particles.

FIG. 1.

Curves A, B, C and C' are as in S. N. Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 63; Curve C'' from the data in Table III of this paper.

In Fig. 1 are collected the changes in the cataphoretic speeds produced on dilution (*vide Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 63). Dilution by changing the environment brings into operation a large number of factors. The hydrogen-ion concentration (as observed after coagulation by solid K_2SO_4 , S. N. Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*) decreases on dilution. The concentration of the free chlorine ions and the total chlorine have been determined directly¹ (Table IV). Assuming² that the concentration of the free ions (hydrogen³ and chlorine) given

¹ The concentrations of the iron and hydrogen ions are subject to uncertainty as they have been indirectly determined. It is proposed to eliminate this uncertainty in a subsequent paper.

² The validity of this assumption is the subject matter of a separate investigation (*vide Introduction*).

³ Cf. Pauli and Matula, *loc. cit.*

in these tables are those of the intermicellary liquid, the concentration of ferric ions present in it, is given by the difference between them. Deducting from the observed specific conductivity of the sol the conductivity contributed by these three ions (Kohlrausch and Holborn, *Das Leitvermögen der Elektrolyte*, 1916), we obtain

FIG. 2.

In the ordinate different units are chosen for convenience of plotting :

Associated chlorine	-1 div. = '0021	origin refers to	'0053N.
Chlorine-ion conc.	-1 div. = '0004	" "	'005N.
H ⁺ -ion conc.	-1 div. = '00004	" "	'00003N.
Sp. conductivity	-1 div. = '0001	" "	000118 r.o.
$\frac{1}{3}$ Fe ⁺⁺⁺ -ion conc.	-1 div. = '00016	" "	'00043N.

the conductivity contributed by the charged micelle and its associated ions. The specific conductivity of the sol also steadily decreases with dilution. The concentration of the free chlorine and hydrogen ions show a remarkable parallelism with the change in the specific conductivity of the sol on dilution (Fig. 2, curves 1, 2, and 3 respectively).

The complicated variation in the cataphoretic speed on dilution is in contrast to the above. The cataphoretic speed of the particles has little effect on the specific conductivity as such, or *vice versa*. In curve 4, Fig. 2 the amount of chlorine per litre 'associated' with the colloidal particles has been plotted against the dilution. This quantity has been calculated on the assumption that the free chlorine-ion concentration gives the chlorine present in the intermicellary liquid. The associated chlorine would then be equal to the excess of the total chlorine (estimated per litre of the original sol) over the free chlorine-ion concentration of each dilution multiplied by the dilution. The associated chlorine does not show the regular variation observed with the other quantities. The changes in the cataphoretic speed cannot also be correlated with it. Fig. 1 shows that considerations of activity coefficients, and ionic strengths are insufficient (Pauli, *loc. cit.*, p. 172; Pennycuick, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1930, p. 1447, and earlier publications).

(b) *Changes produced by Ultrafiltration.*

From Table VIII it appears that the chlorine-ion concentration of the ultrafiltrate is considerably less than that of the free chlorine ions in the sol. Moreover the conductivity of the ultrafiltrate is less than what it would be if the chlorine was present solely as hydrogen chloride. A trace of ferric ions might be assumed to be present.⁴ The possible presence of very fine (amicrons) colloidal particles of iron is also not excluded. The presence of cations other than hydrogen ions is also shown by the excess of the total chlorine over the free chlorine ions in the ultrafiltrate. The liquid obtained after coagulation of the colloid with potassium sulphate has a much higher concentration of 'free' chlorine ions than that of the ultrafiltrate or of the original sol. The residual sol after ultrafiltration has exactly the same chlorine-ion concentration as that of the liquid obtained by coagulation which is possibly a chance coincidence. The total chlorine in the residual sol is greater than that of the original sol but that of the supernatant liquid is less than both these quantities. *Ultrafiltration clearly produces a*

⁴ The thiocyanate test gave a negative result.

change in the composition of the intermicellary fluid. Less of the free chlorine ions pass out and their concentration increases in the residual sol. The smaller conductivity of the latter shows that it is poorer in hydrogen ions.

(c) *The Ultrafiltrate as the Upper Liquid in Cataphoretic Measurements.*

From Table VII it will also be seen that the ultrafiltrate is not satisfactory as the upper liquid. This is shown by the marked difference between the cataphoretic speeds in the upward and downward movements. The constancy between the potential gradient as also the agreement between the upward and downward speeds with the usual upper liquid evidently satisfies the theoretical requirements for a uniform ionic environment. Since this liquid is obtained by adding a trace of concentrated ferric chloride to the liquid obtained after coagulation it seems likely that the latter has a higher hydrogen-ion concentration than that of the intermicellary fluid determined as above. At any rate, these results show (a) that the ultrafiltrate has not the same composition as the intermicellary fluid (b) the liquid obtained by coagulation has a different hydrogen-ion concentration than that of the intermicellary fluid and (c) the use of the ultrafiltrate as an upper liquid in cataphoretic measurements (Kruyt and Willigen *loc. cit.*) is not justified and gives erroneous results in the former instance.

(d) *The Cataphoretic speed in relation to the Composition of the Intermicellary liquid.*

FIG. 3.

In Fig. 3 have been plotted the concentrations of the free hydrogen, iron and chlorine ions against that of the chlorine ions associated with the colloid. It appears that over a considerable range beginning with the first dilution, the associated chlorine remains fairly constant. On either side of this range the associated chlorine decreases with the concentration of the free ions. Assuming that the number of particles per unit volume is proportional to the dilution, curve (4) in Fig. 2 indicates a rapid increase of the number of free chlorine ions in the intermicellary liquid and a corresponding diminution in the number associated with the colloid micelles. In the middle portion of the curve the reverse process appears to take place to a small extent. This is probably associated with the observed increase in the cataphoretic speed after the first dilution. On comparing the manner of variation of the cataphoretic speed (Fig. 1) with the curves in Fig. 3, it is possible to draw a picture as to how the speed depends on the composition of the electrolyte. The number of ferric ions per unit surface of the colloidal particle may be assumed to be determined by the concentration of ferric ions (or rather of hydrogen ions which determine their stability) in the intermicellary liquid. At the first dilution there is a rapid fall in the concentration of these ions, as also in the number of positive electronic charges in the form of ferric ions per unit surface. Possibly each of the ferric ions in the surface hydrolyses and forms ions of the basic residue with two or one free electronic charges [*e.g.*, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}_2$]. The fall in the amount of associated chlorine at the first dilution is indicative of such a change. For the next stages of dilution, the number and type of such complexes do not seem to vary widely with further changes in the concentration of these ions. Curve 4 (Fig. 2) confirms this conclusion. On further dilution, progressive hydrolysis takes place resulting in the removal of chlorine ions from the interface. The increase in the speed at greater dilutions together with the small variation of the associated chlorine for the next two dilutions indicate that with further decrease in the concentration of chlorine ions in the intermicellary liquids, an increasing fraction of the associated chlorine passes from the solid side of the interface to the liquid side.

FIG. 4.

Concentration of KCl in normality; Curve 1 refers to sol A/2 (Table V); Curve 2 refers to sol A/11 (Table VI).

FIG. 5.

Fig. 4 shows that no direct relationship can justifiably be assumed to exist between the cataphoretic speed and ionic strength (Pauli, Pennycuick, *loc. cit.*) on the basis of the Debye-Hückel theory. For though the added electrolyte is present in concentration and is the same in both, the forms of the two curves are widely different. Also the valencies of the colloidal particles are unknown and the sol is a polydisperse one. It is also to be observed that no simple relationship exists between the initial speed and the coagulating concentration. In fact the sol with higher initial speed has a lower speed as also a lower coagulating concentration at the coagulation point. The curves further show a drop in the cataphoretic speed after coagulation with progress of time. These observations are in agreement with the previous observations with arsenious sulphide sol in this laboratory. The small but definite difference in the cataphoretic speed at the coagulation point and the shapes of the two curves show that the supposed existence of a critical coagulating potential is not borne out by facts.

*The Cataphoretic Speed and the Surface Density of
the Electrical charge.*

The density of the charge is the one electrical factor which admits of a direct relationship with the fixation of ions on the solid side of the interface (see *Trans. Faraday, Soc., loc. cit.*; *Phil. Mag., loc. cit.*). The assumption that the density is proportional to the cataphoretic speed requires theoretical and experimental justification. It can be experimentally tested as follows. We shall first define what we have called the 'equivalent concentration' of the colloidal particles. It is equal to the number of colloidal particles per litre multiplied by the *average* number of electronic charges per particle expressed in terms of the customary unit in electrochemistry (96540 coulombs). It can be calculated if the cataphoretic speed, the mobility of the free ions associated with the colloidal particle and the conductivity of the colloidal particles are known. If Q is the number of electrochemical equivalents (of the micelle ions) per litre and δ is the sum of the equivalent conductivities of the associated free chlorine ion and of the micelle ions then we have:

$$P = Q \cdot \delta \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where P is thousand times the specific conductivity of the colloidal

particles as distinct from that of the intermicellary liquid. The equivalent conductivity of the charged colloidal particle (micelle ion) is given by the cataphoretic speed multiplied by the electrochemical unit of electricity. On the assumption that the cataphoretic speed U (which is independent of the size) is proportional to the density of the electric charge, we have $U = K.n$ (2) where n is the number of electronic charges per unit surface. The actual number per particle is proportional to the surface. We then have $Q = n.N.S$ (3) where N is the number of colloidal particles per litre and S is equal to the *arithmetic mean* surface of the particles. Further $\delta = (U + V)F$... (4) where V is the speed of the associated *free* anions assumed to be of one sort only, whence it follows that

$$P = n. N. S. (U + V)F = \frac{U}{K}. N. S. (U + V)F \dots (5). \text{ Relationship}$$

(5) can be tested for different dilutions assuming further as is usual that the number of particles per unit volume is proportional to the dilution.

The product $\delta.Q$ can be obtained from the following relation

$$R = \alpha x + \beta y + \gamma z + \delta.Q \dots (6)$$

where R is thousand times the specific conductivity of the sol, α , β , γ are respectively the equivalent conductivities of chlorine, hydrogen and ferric ions and x , y , z are respectively the number of gram equivalents of these ions per litre of the sol.

From the equivalent concentration of the colloidal particle, m , calculated from equation (2) and the number of gram mole, p of ferric oxide per litre of the sol, it is possible to calculate the number of molecules of ferric oxide, m/p , with which one electronic unit of charge is associated (*vide* column 12 of Table IX). It is interesting to note that the reciprocals of the sequantities (excepting the last values) fairly represent the trend of the curve (Fig. 5) showing the variation in the cataphoretic speed with dilution. It should be emphasised that some of the values have been obtained in an indirect manner and that several assumptions have been made which though often accepted as true, require adequate justification by further experiments. The error in calculating $\delta.Q$ increases as the dilution increases. Also the silver-silver chloride electrode is not completely satisfactory for these solutions.

In Table IX are collected the data for different dilutions of the sol as follows:—Column 1 gives the dilutions of the sol; 2, the

cataphoretic speeds (u) at 35° in cm./sec. per volt/cm. $\times 10^5$; 3, the value for $u' = uF$, in reciprocal ohms at room temperature ($20^\circ.5$); column 4 gives P , the specific conductivity of the sol at $20^\circ.5$; columns 5, 6, 7, 8 give the equivalent concentrations per litre respectively of free chlorine ions (x), the total chloride, hydrogen ions (y) and iron ions (z); column 9 gives the value for the product $\delta.Q$, where δ is the sum of the equivalent conductivities of chlorine ions α and u' , that of the micelle ion extrapolated for $20^\circ.5$ assuming the speed to be inversely proportional to the viscosity. In columns 10 and 11 are given the equivalent concentrations of colloidal particles calculated as explained above and the number of gm. moles of ferric oxide per litre; m/p , the number of molecules of ferric oxide with which one electronic charge is associated, is given in the column 12.

The concentrations of the ions in the following table have been calculated assuming complete dissociation. The activity coefficients can be obtained from the equivalent conductivity by a method of approximation and the values if corrected in this manner give better agreement.

TABLE IX.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Pure sol	51.43	35.16	.001039	.003166N	.0104N	.000369N	.00279N	.0005225	.0050N	.0422M	8.4
1:1	41.32	28.25	.000560	.00206N	Estimated. .0052N	.000316N	.001744N	.0002040	.0021N	.0211M	10.0
1:3	49.79	34.03	.000308	.001042N	Calculated. .0026N	.000098N	.0009439N	0.001446	.0014N	.0105M	7.5
1:5	53.51	36.58	.000217	.0006982N	Calculated. .00173N	.0000619N	.0006363N	.0001087	.0010N	.00703M	7.0
1:10	58.41	39.93	.000118	.0004656N	Calculated. .000945N	.0000271N	.0004385N	.0000495	.00045N	.00383M	8.5

In conclusion it is necessary to emphasise that some of the conclusions of the present paper are of a tentative character.

